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Advancing Robust Governance in Turbulent Times: The Role of Multi-Level Governance, Hybrid Governance, and Negotiated Societal Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

New research argues that robust governance based on flexible adaptation and proactive innovation is needed in order to uphold core public functions, purposes, and values in times of societal turbulence. However, we have limited knowledge of the conditions for enhancing robust governance. To fill that knowledge gap, we ask: How can multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and societal intelligence contribute to the development of robust responses to the proliferation of complex and turbulent problems? To answer this pertinent question, we draw on relevant literatures to conceptualize each of the three governance factors and develop a set of theoretically derived conjectures about their impact on robust governance. We also discuss the combined effects of the three governance factors as well as the limits to robust governance. Finally, we draw some lessons for practitioners and sketch out an agenda for further research.

Human history has been marked by recurring spells of societal turbulence in which communities have been marred by war, strife, hunger, economic decline, and natural disasters (Louçã 1997; Gat 2008). Today, the concurrence of globalization, a changing world order, new disruptive technologies, and political disalignment seems to render spells of turbulence even more frequent and enduring (Rosenau 1997; Drucker 2012; Ansell et al. 2025). Consequently, public leaders are facing a growing number of unpredictable societal dynamics triggered by economic recession, refugee crises, pandemics, energy shortages, climate chaos, military conflicts, etc. (Ansell and Trondal 2018). Indeed, they seem to spend much more time and energy putting out fires than formulating and achieving collective goals.

After a relatively stable postwar period with steady economic growth, social peace, and predictable bureaucratic regulation,

we are witnessing heightened societal turbulence that challenges the ability of the public sector to uphold its core functions, purposes, and values (McDonald III et al. 2022). Recently, the COVID-19 pandemic demonstrated how health systems were jeopardized, while lockdowns disrupted the normal functioning of the public sector and impeded the delivery of welfare services to citizens (Clemente-Suárez et al. 2021). To maintain stability during turbulent times and continue achieving key public goals and ambitions, the public sector must flexibly adapt and proactively innovate its approaches to service delivery, societal and economic regulation, and political governance (Ansell et al. 2021). We thus argue that robust governance based on a combination of flexible adaptation and proactive innovation is the key to achieving robust governance in the face of crisis-induced turbulence (Ansell et al. 2023, 2024; Capano and Woo 2018).

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By seeking “to change in order to preserve” (Ansell et al. 2015), robust governance provides an alternative to “agility,” aimed at harnessing turbulence to radically reinvent private companies, as well as to “resilience,” aimed at restoring the status quo ante of communities exposed to turbulent events. Recent research has demonstrated the need for robust governance in turbulent times (Capano and Toth 2023; Capano and Woo 2017, 2018) and provided a repertoire of strategies enabling public governors to provide robust governance in the face of unpredictable societal dynamics (Ansell et al. 2021, 2024). While our knowledge of the conditions for enhancing robust governance is limited, our “informed hunch” is that robust governance is predicated on: (1) the presence of *multi-level governance* that generates crosscutting interactions that in turn facilitate and support flexible adaptation and proactive innovation of public policy, regulation, and services in response to reports about changing circumstances (Migone 2020; Kuhlmann and Franzke 2022); (2) access to and past experiences with *hybrid forms of governance* that facilitate flexible mixing and matching of organizational forms and governing tools in the face of turbulence (Eckhard et al. 2021; Nõmmik et al. 2023); and (3) the presence of *negotiated societal intelligence* harnessing different forms of knowledge to foster and authorize the deployment of novel and changing forms of governance (Kettle et al. 2014; Van Enst et al. 2014). Our selection of these governance factors is supported by how societal turbulence permeates and affects various levels of governance, challenges existing tools of governance, and necessitates the integration of different forms of knowledge. It also supported by the observation that the achievement of governance robustness based on adaptation and innovation requires horizontal and vertical coordination through multi-level governance, a pragmatic combination and repurposing of extant tools through hybrid forms of governance, and a combination of alignment and learning through negotiated societal intelligence. Based on these conjectures, our guiding research question is: *How can key aspects of multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence contribute to the development of robust responses to the proliferation of complex and turbulent problems triggered by crises and disruptive events?*

To address this pertinent question concerning the conditions contributing to the emergence of robust governance, the first section defines the basic concepts of societal turbulence and robust governance and discusses their interrelationship. The next three sections draw on relevant literature to conceptualize each of the three governance factors and develop a set of theoretically derived conjectures regarding their impact on robust governance. The following sections discuss the combined effects of the three governance factors together with the limits to robust governance. The conclusion summarizes the argument, draws some lessons for practitioners, and provides an agenda for further research.

1 | Robust Governance in Response to Societal Turbulence

After World War II, many countries expanded their public sector to solve some simple and “tame” problems in the fields of health, education, and social welfare. Both the nature of these problems

and their likely solutions were clear to political decision-makers, allowing them to delegate problem-solving to professionally trained employees in rapidly growing public bureaucracies. In the 1960s and 1970s, however, researchers and practitioners identified a new type of complex and “wicked” problem found in most policy areas, but perhaps most visibly in the field of public planning, which was ridden with failures (Churchman 1967; Hall 1980; Rittel and Webber 1973). Wicked problems are tangled, have many complexly related causes, and their uniqueness means that they have no standard solution. Moreover, they emerge in problem settings comprising multiple stakeholders with different interests, which gives rise to goal conflicts precluding trial and error. To tackle these intractable problems, researchers recommend that public bureaucracies involve relevant and affected actors who can help diagnose problems and agree on “good enough” solutions (Head and Alford 2015; Roberts 2000; Weber and Khademian 2008).

Recent research emphasizes the *temporal dimension* of wicked problems and discusses turbulent problems that, in addition to being cognitively and politically complex, are also unexpected, unpredictable, uncertain, inconsistent, and constantly mutating (Ansell and Trondal 2017; Ansell et al. 2021, 2024; LaPorte 2007). Although crosscutting collaboration among distributed actors remains valuable for jointly assessing changing problems and continuously refining solutions (Scognamiglio et al. 2022), collaborative governance networks may struggle with acting swiftly and lacking formal authority. It has therefore been recommended that governance networks be carefully metagoverned (Peters et al. 2022).

The concept of *turbulence* has long been used in everyday language to describe disorderly movements within crowds of animals, children, and troops (Ansell et al. 2024). In the early twentieth century, the concept gained increasing popularity in fluid mechanics, where it refers to unpredictable fluid dynamics found in stormy weather, cloud movements, river currents, and fire whirls (Eckert 2012; Schmitt 2017). In the social sciences, references to “turbulence” began appearing in the late-1960s (Easton 1965; Emery and Trist 1965; Waldo 1971), and the term is currently used in social science disciplines, such as international politics (Brown et al. 2008; Rosenau 1997), macro- and microeconomics (Ashworth and Heyndels 2002; Tsai and Yang 2014), natural resource management (Allen et al. 2011; Dobbs et al. 2021), and public administration (Ansell et al. 2017; Carstensen et al. 2023; Nolte et al. 2020; Zhong et al. 2023).

Societal turbulence can be defined as a persistent or temporary condition characterized by unpredictable and unstable dynamics resulting from the contingent interaction of variable, inconsistent, and uncertain events, developments, and demands (Ansell et al. 2024). A basic level of turbulence always exists in society, as complex and open systems cannot fully shield themselves from emerging tensions, dysfunctions, and critical incidents. However, societal turbulence may spike when various events, developments, and demands contingently combine to create a perfect storm. Heightened turbulence may also be triggered by crises that are not effectively contained and spill over into multiple sectors, areas, and organizations. Unintended negative consequences of crisis management may also create waves of turbulence. While

turbulence may be crisis-induced, high levels of turbulence may persist even after avoiding the potentially cataclysmic consequences of a crisis.

Societal turbulence occurs at various scales: the breakdown of the *Pax Americana* has triggered new global power dynamics and disruptive conflicts; national governance is being disrupted by economic globalization, technological innovation, political scandals, and new forms of social and political polarization; and public organizations may be rattled by interdepartmental conflicts, conflicting goals, clashing governance strategies, and the uncertain impact of administrative reforms. Moreover, disruptive events at one level of governance may negatively affect what happens at another level (Ansell and Trondal 2018). Finally, trans-local effects may arise when war, poverty, hunger, or climate change in one locality triggers an unexpected influx of refugees into another locality.

Due to the increasing interconnection and causal linkages across scales, countries, sectors, and organizations, as well as the prevalence of overlapping crises, societal turbulence appears to have become the new normal (Ansell et al. 2024). This development has important consequences for public governance (Ansell et al. 2017). Unlike *crisis*, which refers to a critical moment of upheaval and stress leading to either system collapse or recovery (Rosenthal et al. 2001), *turbulence* does not necessarily pose any immediate threat to social, economic, or political systems. Indeed, many societies have grown accustomed to relatively high levels of turbulence. Nevertheless, spells of heightened societal turbulence may seriously impede the ability of the public sector to uphold its key functions, purposes, and values.

Spiking societal turbulence calls for *robust governance*. In everyday language, “robustness” is associated with strength, vigor, and sturdiness. Scientific references to robustness begin to diversify in the 1990s (see Jen 2005). In chemistry, there is a focus on robust chemical processes (Song 2004), dynamics (Deng et al. 2010), and substances (Zang et al. 2021). In biology, robustness is a long-recognized property of living systems that is analyzed both at the cellular level (Stelling et al. 2004), at the level of complex biological systems (Krakauer 2006), and ecosystems (Cai and Liu 2016; Kitano 2004). In engineering, robustness is associated with the design of systems with a functional reliability in the presence of probable and improbable failures (Carlson and Doyle 2002; Taguchi et al. 2000), while in computer science it refers to software and computer networks being able to perform correctly in situations with expected user or data failure (Willinger and Doyle 2005).

In the social sciences, discussions of robustness emerged in the work of Leifer (1991), Ansell and Padgett (1993), and Anderies and Janssen (2013), who argued that robust action aims to keep future options open. Economists discuss the robustness of market economies, which can be shown to be robust in the sense of an ability to withstand the stresses and strains wrought by human imperfections (Pennington 2011). Environmental planners advocate for sustainability strategies that are robust against a wide range of plausible climate-change scenarios and capable of performing effectively amid unexpected events or catastrophes (Lempert and Schlesinger 2000). Disaster management

researchers claim that robust disaster relief may be provided by combining pre-positioned relief supplies with limited amounts of relief supplies procured after the disaster (Velasquez et al. 2020). Policy analysts focus on robust policy designs that are flexible enough to perform well across different contexts and to survive external shocks and internal perturbations (Capano and Woo 2018; Ferraro et al. 2015). To illustrate, Howlett (2019) argues that the intentional sequencing of policy instruments is the key to ensuring robustness in turbulent times, and Carstensen et al. (2023) praise the role of bricolage, which combines and repurposes tools from competing and co-existing governance paradigms.

Based on an interdisciplinary review of the robustness literature, Ansell et al. (2024) define robust governance as the capacity to ensure the formulation and implementation of effective and legitimate public value solutions in response to heightened turbulence by means of flexible adaptation and the proactive innovation of public policy, regulation, and service production. While “adaptation” involves the modification of existing solutions, “innovation” involves the development and implementation of new solutions that break with common wisdom and practices. When adapting and innovating public value solutions, public governors may also slightly redefine the functions, purposes, and values that they aim to uphold. Hence, robust governance may both transform the *modus operandi* of the public sector and rearticulate its overall objectives (Howlett and Ramesh 2023; Jen 2005).

The robust governance concept offers an alternative to classical responses to turbulence, which offer a hard choice between resilience and agility. While some researchers have stressed the importance of adaptation as a part of dynamic resilience (Chen et al. 2022; Deloukas and Apostolopoulou 2017; Windle 2011), the core of the classical static-resilience strategy is to “bounce back” by restoring the *status quo ante* that the rise of turbulence disrupted (Folke 2006; Holling 1973; Walker et al. 2006). The problem with this strategy is that it precludes the possibility of exploiting turbulence to get to a new and better place by means of “bouncing forward” (Manyena et al. 2011). While some researchers continue to talk about strategies for bouncing forward to new and better solutions as *resilience* (Hynes et al. 2020), we believe *robustness* to be a better and more precise term, as it captures the endeavor to adapt *and* innovate in the face of turbulence.

If the resilience strategy is too backward-looking, the alternative agility strategy goes too much in the opposite direction by praising the readiness to embrace, learn from, and harness turbulence; and possibly even orchestrate perturbations and disruptions to stimulate creativity, perpetual innovation, and revolutionary breakthroughs (Johnson 2018; Light 2005; Room 2011; Sarasvathy et al. 2014). While this agility strategy may work well for small entrepreneurial businesses engaged in a restless hunt for profitability, most public sector agencies aim for ambidexterity that seeks to combine the stable delivery of core tasks with innovative adjustments (Palm and Lilja 2017).

In sum, robust governance aims to avoid both the Scylla of the backward-looking resilience strategy and the Charybdis of

the radically transformative agility strategy by insisting that, during periods of societal turbulence, the modus operandi of the public sector must be transformed to uphold some key public functions, purposes, and values. Hence, rather than seeing change and stability as mutually exclusive opposites, the robustness concept tends to view change and stability as mutually conditioning: change is needed to secure some degree of stability, while the demand for stability guides and controls the change process (Ansell et al. 2023; Carlson and Doyle 2002).

2 | Strategies for Achieving Robustness

Robust governance can be achieved through a combination of different emerging *robustness strategies* that social and political actors invent “on the fly” while drawing on previous experiences. Drawing on extant theories of organizational crisis response, we can compile a list of seven actor-driven robustness strategies showing what robust governance entails in practice:

1. *Build redundancy, slack, and buffering.* Landau (1969) argues that “redundancy,” defined as extra components that are not strictly necessary for a program to function, is important for reducing errors, while Capano and Woo (2018) find that designing redundancies into public policy enhances policy robustness. Classical organizational theory claims that organizational “slack,” defined as excess resources, and “buffering,” defined as mechanisms that dampen external demands, are helpful for managing challenging circumstances and external disruptions, as they create leeway for reflection and innovation (March and Simon 1958; Thompson 1967).
2. *Plan for surprises.* While planning ahead is notoriously difficult for organizations in turbulent environments (Schulman 2022; Weick and Sutcliffe 2015), they may be vigilant in the sense of paying attention to early signs of disruptive change and taking the necessary steps to respond (Schoemaker and Day 2021). They may also rely on scenario planning, which enables them to identify and adapt to emerging turbulence (Ramírez and Selsky 2016), or plan for innovation by considering hypothetical futures (Liedtka 2000; Tassabehji and Isherwood 2014). Finally, organizations may preemptively establish “rules of exception” that allow for deviation from standard procedures during extraordinary events (LaPorte 2007).
3. *Scale governance responses.* “Scaling” refers to the process of taking something (be it policy, governance, or a service solution), and scaling it up or down to match new and changing demands caused by increasing turbulence (Hsu 2009). One way to scale is to (de-)mobilize resources; for example, by hiring new staff or recruiting and involving volunteers. Alternatively, existing personnel may be used more flexibly, giving them new tasks for shorter periods of time. Finally, scaling may involve efforts to turn pilot innovations into policies and programs (Simmons et al. 2007).
4. *Become bricoleurs and modularize solutions.* Carstensen et al. (2023) define bricolage as the effort to reuse, recombine, and repurpose existing tools and resources. Bricolage

is easy where tools are modular and can be flexibly combined in multiple ways to suit different purposes. As noted by Schilling (2000, 315), modularity “enable[s] heterogeneous inputs to be recombined into a variety of heterogeneous configurations.” The cost of modularity and bricolage is a loss of specialization in tools and resources, but the gain is a flexible applicability that is *valuable in turbulent times*.

5. *Be ready to improvise, probe, and learn.* Improvisation based on skilled intuition is necessary in turbulent situations where there is pressure to act swiftly—but no available script (Ravazzi 2024). It can be facilitated by a pragmatic “probe-and-learn” strategy that responds creatively to new and changing circumstances through measured experimental actions that seek to develop and test prototypes to promote rapid learning in real-life contexts (Ansell and Bartenberger 2016). Mendonça and colleagues (Mendonça et al. 2004) argue that such experimentation requires “safe environments” in which the failure to learn is acceptable. If time is short, such environments must be readily available. The solution is often small-scale experimentation, where the costs of failure are limited and scaling occurs when the experiment is deemed successful.
6. *Create governance discourses based on multivocality.* Ferraro et al. (2015, 373) define multivocality as a “discursive and material activity that sustains different interpretations among various audiences with different evaluation criteria, in a manner that promotes coordination without requiring explicit consensus.” Ambiguous crisis communication can help public decision-makers to gain support for new solutions from various stakeholders and may also allow them to flexibly adjust their course of action flexibly by avoiding commitments to specific agendas and precise solutions (Ansell and Padgett 1993). Multivocality enhances the maneuverability of public governors, enabling them to respond quickly to changing circumstances, and it allows them to build coalitions of change-makers.
7. *Promote accountable autonomy.* Robust governance can be achieved by granting the latitude necessary to governance actors at different levels to respond flexibly and in a timely manner to unforeseen and uncertain developments while adhering to general goals and guidelines for which they will ultimately be held accountable (Deverell 2010; Fung 2001; Howlett et al. 2018; Light 2005). This can be achieved by involving local actors in the implementation of key public tasks and regulations and encouraging them to adapt overall governance strategies to the changing conditions on the ground. Promoting accountable autonomy requires the empowerment of local actors together with mechanisms for ensuring their accountability.

The list of robust governance strategies presented above is not definitive, as more strategies will be developed in the future, but there is already quite a repertoire of strategies from which public governors can draw in their pursuit of robust governance. There is no guarantee that the use of shifting combinations of robustness strategies will succeed in upholding key public functions, goals, and values, but sticking to old formats and standard solutions will most likely enhance turbulence and further undermine public functions, purposes, and values.

FIGURE 1 | Conceptual model relating key governance factors to robust governance in the face of turbulence. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/padm.20011)]

3 | Governance Factors Supporting Robustness

New research on robust governance emphasizes the impact of institutional conditions in the pursuit of robust governance (Ansell et al. 2024) but hardly reflects on the role that various governance factors may play for the development of robust governance responses in times of heightened societal turbulence. To compensate for this benign neglect, our focus is on how three important *governance factors* can support robust governance: multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence.

Briefly stated, we expect that: (1) interaction between public and private actors at multiple levels of governance may prompt and support the adaptation and innovation of public value solutions (Migone 2020; Kuhlmann and Franzke 2022); (2) hybrid forms of governance, legality, and democracy will allow actors to mix and match different tools and solutions in the pursuit of adaptation and innovation (Eckhard et al. 2021; Nömmik et al. 2023); and (3) negotiated knowledge production involving elected politicians and their administrative aides, scientific and professional experts, and lay actors will allow local governance actors to detect problems and challenges while expanding their range of possible solutions, thereby facilitating adaptation and innovation (Kettle et al. 2014; Van Enst et al. 2014). While multi-level governance and negotiated societal intelligence connect relevant actors both vertically and horizontally to foster alignment and learning, hybrid governance expands the toolbox from which the actors may draw when seeking to tackle crisis-induced turbulence. Moreover, while extant literature has highlighted other important governance factors, such as professional roles and identities (Kuiper et al. 2024) and forms of leadership and management (Lund and Andersen 2023), the synergistic dynamics between multi-level governance, hybrid forms of governance, and negotiated societal intelligence provide a strong foundation for understanding the conditions necessary

for robust governance. Finally, it should be noted that since the present study is based on literature focused on Western countries, the validity of our argument does not extend beyond that specific context.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual model underlying our argument, revealing how the three governance factors affect the strategic efforts to produce robust governance aimed at moderating the disruptive impact of societal turbulence on the production of societal outcomes that uphold key public functions, purposes, and values.

To further explore the impact of the three governance factors on the ability to govern robustly during periods of turbulence, the following three sections define these factors and explain how they may create the conditions for the emergence of robust governance.

3.1 | Conceptualizing Multi-Level Governance and Exploring Its Impact on Robust Governance

The attempts made by public and private actors in a networked locality—be it a city, municipality, or province—to meet heightened societal turbulence with robust governance are conditioned by political and administrative action taking place at other levels of government. Hence, local governance networks are embedded in a multi-level governance system that both enables and constrains local action through the provision of instruction, regulation, advice, and inspiration (Caponio et al. 2023).

The multi-level governance debate has mushroomed since the publication of the seminal works by Hooghe and Marks (2001), Bache and Flinders (2004), and Piattoni (2010), leading to competing definitions of multi-level governance. One dominant

strand of the literature defines it as a dispersion of the authority of national governments across a wider spectrum of interdependent and yet autonomous public and private organizations operating at different local, regional, national, and supranational scales (Bache and Flinders 2004; Hooghe and Marks 2001; Marks 1993). In the case of the European Union, the dispersion of state authority has created a new complex governance system characterized by multiple overlapping and complexly related jurisdictions. In response to both top-down pressures for European integration at the political apex and bottom-up demands for decentralization, state authority has become dispersed within and beyond nation states, producing a multi-layered polity based on interaction between states, levels of government, and public and private actors, each of whom hold a certain amount of power (Hooghe et al. 2013).

While debates on European integration have seen multi-level governance as a grand governance architecture in which authority and power are widely distributed and contingently activated, a new strand of literature tends to see multi-level governance as a condition for public policymaking. Policymaking increasingly takes place in multi-level governance settings in which policies are uploaded, downloaded, and subject to negotiation (Piattoni 2010; Scholten 2013). Indeed, the processes through which policy is formulated and implemented not only involve different levels of government but also public, private, and civic actors (Alcantara and Nelles 2014; Alcantara et al. 2016). The emerging literature on multi-level governance as a prerequisite for policymaking converges on identifying three core features: (1) different levels of government are simultaneously involved in policymaking; (2) non-governmental actors are participating at different levels; and (3) relationships between different levels of government and with non-governmental actors take the form of network-based collaboration and consensus-building (Alcantara and Nelles 2014; Caponio and Jones-Correa 2018). A key strength of this new conceptualization of multi-level governance is that it pays attention to both horizontal and vertical relationships while considering both formal and informal interaction processes based on complex interdependencies between distributed actors. Moreover, its focus on policymaking in relation to specific issues, problems, and challenges renders it well suited to exploring the impact of multi-level interaction on robust governance.

Multi-level governance plays a key role in emergency responses based on the widely used Incident Management System, which requires the strong engagement of multiple levels of government together with collaborative interaction between public and private actors (Arendt and Alesh 2015; Comfort and Kapucu 2006; Sylves 2020). Local governments are expected to act quickly to emergencies based on pre-designed emergency management plans that typically involve the formation of an ad hoc interagency steering group and the mobilization of local neighborhoods and voluntary organizations. Regional (or state) government must coordinate the work of local governments and liaise with central (or federal) government. The latter defines the conditions for local and regional governments to request financial, logistical, and operational support from national emergency agencies, which will eventually work through and with (rather than in place of) local actors (Sylves 2020). In transborder crises,

national governments will share information and knowledge and engage in pluricentric coordination and learning, possibly also receiving support from supranational or international governance institutions (Schmidt 2020). Of particular relevance to our argument, recent studies suggest that, despite some initial slowness, multi-level governance systems contributed to successful pandemic responses by stimulating flexibility and tailoring responses to local challenges (Migone 2020; Kuhlmann and Franzke 2022; Carroll et al. 2025).

Coordinated interaction between actors from different levels and sectors is notoriously difficult in crisis situations in which uncertainty, complexity, and time pressure are considerable and the circumstances change in unpredictable ways. Providing robust governance in the face of crisis-induced turbulence therefore depends on the form of the interaction between distributed actors from different levels. Hence, we stipulate that the more multi-level governance arrangements facilitate two-way communication between relevant public and private actors that is both frequent and dense, problem-driven, learning-focused, and based on swift trust and the recognition of the need (see Blomqvist and Cook 2018), the more they will contribute to robust governance. Along these lines, Klinke (2017) argues that dynamic multi-level governance based on inclusiveness, institutional adaptiveness, and differentiated deliberation between distributed actors enhances the prospects for transformative governance in crisis situations. Similarly, Pahl-Wostl (2009) contends that informal multi-level networks play a crucial role in adaptive learning processes, and Gonzales-Iwanciw et al. (2020) find that multi-level governance arrangements that stimulate learning may enhance adaptation and perhaps even policy and governance innovation. In essence, problem-focused interaction in multi-level governance systems may help to circulate information and knowledge, reformulate problem understandings and common objectives, flexibly adjust public policy and regulation, and support local innovation based on joint learning and authorization of solutions tailored to local conditions.

Based on these observations, we formulate four conjectures regarding the impact of multi-level governance on the pursuit of robust governance (see also Caponio et al. 2023):

1. Governance becomes more robust as interactions between public and private actors across multiple levels become more frequent, dense, trustful, and learning-based.
2. Governance is more robust when higher-level government actors solicit and receive policy input from lower-level governmental and non-governmental actors, thereby enabling the adjustment of laws, regulations, and recommendations to changing conditions.
3. Governance is more robust when lower-level government actors interact with higher-level government actors to garner support for flexible and exceptional local actions.
4. Governance is more robust when distributed actors from different levels and sectors deliberate on equal footing in various formal and informal arenas to align goals and coordinate plans and actions in response to new developments.

These four conjectures highlight how interactivity in multi-level governance systems can stimulate mutual learning, centralized policy adjustments based on soliciting bottom-up input, support for local action through the cultivation of contacts with higher-level authorities, and deliberative coordination and planning, all of which in turn will contribute to robust governance.

3.2 | Conceptualizing Hybrid Governance and Exploring Its Impact on Robust Governance

Robust governance presupposes the ability to adapt flexibly and proactively innovate public value solutions in response to unpredictable dynamics within public organizations and their external environment. Adaptation and innovation may both benefit from the tendency of the public sector to host different forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation that can be creatively combined and redirected to meet shifting demands (Nõmmik et al. 2023). While competing governance paradigms, forms of democracy, and types of legal regulation have evolved over time, they tend to co-exist in varying and shifting relations of dominance (Torfing et al. 2020). Since many public tasks require a combination of elements from different types of governance, democracy, and legal regulation (Jessop 2016), the interest in the role and impact of different forms of hybridity has been increasing (Brandsen and Karré 2011; Koppenjan et al. 2019; Skelcher and Smith 2015).

The co-existence of different forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation—together with the hybrid combination of different elements in a purposeful mixing and matching—enables public governors to adapt and innovate in the face of turbulence through the creation of changing configurations of practices, tools, and instruments. While the co-existing forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulations provide the raw material to create new forms of hybrid governance, the already existing hybrid configurations help to encourage (or even justify) the creation of new hybrid configurations. Hence, attempts at promoting robust governance (e.g., through redundancy, modularization, bricolage, or improvisation) are path-dependent in the sense that they are conditioned by the pre-existence of different forms of governance and their hybrid combinations. Let us closely examine the creation of co-existing forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation, as well as the argument in favor of hybrid governance, before returning to the question of how governance hybridity may spur robust governance.

Since the early twentieth century, the public sector has gradually become organized in accordance with the Weberian model of bureaucracy. Hence, rational legal authority was exercised by public-spirited civil servants applying a combination of hierarchical governance, horizontal specialization, and rule-bound discretion (Wilson 1989). Public bureaucracy came under growing attack from public choice theorists, who described public bureaucracies as overly rigid, populated by self-interested civil servants, and guilty of delivering services that are too poor and costly due to a lack of competition (Downs 1967; Niskanen 1971). Bureaucracy-bashing gave way to the introduction of New Public Management-inspired reforms combining privatization,

outsourcing, and the commercialization of public service production with performance management based on goal-setting, performance measurement, and conditional rewards and punishments (Hood 1991; Osborne and Gaebler 1993). NPM was later criticized for contributing to the fragmentation of the public sector (Rhodes 1997) and turning public employees into cynics due to its emphasis on monitoring, control, and transactional leadership, which crowds out task motivation and public service motivation (Moynihan 2010). These problems were addressed by advocates of New Public Governance (Osborne 2010), who recommended the formation of collaborative networks and partnerships (Kickert et al. 1997) and the introduction of trust-based management (Torfing and Bentzen 2020). The changing public governance regimes have shifted the emphasis from hierarchy, via markets, to networks, which offers competing ideas about how the public sector should be governed. However, the emergence of new governance paradigms has not eradicated the old ones; rather, new and old governance paradigms seem to be competing and coexisting in ways that provide opportunities for contingent combinations (Torfing et al. 2020).

We find similar development patterns in relation to democracy (Hendriks 2019) and legal regulation (Castellucci 2012), where competing forms of democracy and law appear to co-exist. Representative democracy builds on the idea that voters elect political representatives who make decisions on their behalf (Dahl 1966), but it has been criticized for providing insufficient opportunity for intensely affected citizens to participate more directly and actively in public decision-making (Della Porta 2013). Consequently, we have seen the introduction of direct democracy based on public referendums aimed at conveying popular opinions on substantial issues to the political decision-makers (Papadopoulos 2013) and the growth of more participatory and deliberative forms of democracy in which citizens are invited to discuss problems and solutions, sometimes even making political recommendations in mini-publics, citizen juries, and digital consultation processes (Nabatchi and Leighninger 2015). In many countries, these various forms of democracy exist side-by-side in a kind of compound democracy, sometimes being deliberately combined in hybrid forms of democracy (Sørensen and Torfing 2019).

Likewise, substantial law that precisely prescribes the rules that public authorities must follow when dealing with particular cases (Campbell 2004) has been supplemented by framework law, which defines broad policy goals and leaves the achievement of the goals to local actors on the basis of their discretion (Knuth and Vidar 2011). However, the prescriptive approach cannot effectively encompass the demands of different and shifting contexts (Baldwin 1990). Consequently, framework law is being supplemented by reflexive law aimed at structuring decision-making by creating procedures that regulate which public and private actors should be involved, when, and how in legal adjudication based on joint decision-making (Teubner 1983). The new forms of legal regulation are typically layered atop the old ones and occasionally combined in the creation of legal hybrids (Sand 2012).

The competing and co-existing forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation provide rich opportunities to create different forms of hybrid governance, hybrid democracy, and

hybrid law based on a mix-and-match strategy aimed at creating constructive synergies in a particular crisis while dealing with the tensions that may arise. Public governors may also create meta-hybrids that combine shifting configurations of governance, democracy, and legal regulation to match changes in a turbulent world (Nõmmik et al. 2023).

While hybridity is a growing theme in public governance and administration (Brandsen and Karré 2011; Koppenjan et al. 2019; Meuleman 2019; Røiseland and Sørensen 2024), the hybridity perspective has remained marginal in the crisis management literature—although some exceptions exist (but see Lee and Wong 2021). However, new research on robust governance praises hybridity as a key condition for adaptation and innovation during periods of heightened turbulence (Carstensen et al. 2023). The basic assumption of this new research is that governance will be more robust if different paradigmatic forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation coexist and if there are strong traditions of and experience with hybrid combinations of all sorts (Nõmmik et al. 2023). In short, the availability of different governance components and prior positive experience with combining them in diverse and evolving ways to exploit complementary strengths while compensating for weaknesses facilitates robust governance.

Based on this assumption, we present four conjectures about the potentially positive impact of hybrid governance on robust governance:

1. Governance is more robust, the more that different forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation co-exist and provide raw material for improvisation, experimentation, bricolage, etc.
2. Governance is more robust the stronger the tradition is for combining bureaucratic governance based on hierarchy with competitive forms of market governance and collaborative forms of network governance.
3. Governance is more robust, the more positive experience there is with combining different forms of representative democracy, direct democracy, and participatory and deliberative democracy.
4. Governance is more robust, the more precedence there is for mixing substantial law, framework law, and reflexive law.

These four conjectures capture the impact of the available diversity of governance, democracy, and legal regulation, as well as the influence of the prior experience with their flexible recombination on efforts to enhance robust governance.

3.3 | Conceptualizing Negotiated Societal Intelligence and Exploring Its Impact on Robust Governance

Robust governance involves adaptive and innovative problem-solving, which in turn hinges on collective wisdom (Landemore and Elster 2012; Sloman and Fernbach 2017) and collective intelligence (Boucher et al. 2023; Landemore 2017). The collective wisdom and intelligence required to understand and address complex and changing problems are enhanced by involving a

plurality of actors with complementary competences, ideas, and forms of knowledge. Tapping into the knowledge of a diverse group of actors and stimulating mutual learning tend to outperform individual efforts with respect to problem analysis, prognostication, creative problem-solving, etc. (Boucher et al. 2023).

Different groups of actors, such as politicians and their administrative aides, scientific and professional experts, and lay actors, including users, citizens, neighborhoods, and civil society organizations, all have access to particular forms of data and information, and they all possess forms of knowledge that, when applied in creative problem-solving, construct a *societal intelligence* that allows actors to interpret, analyze, and act on turbulent events competently (De Angelis 2013; Russo and van Dooren 2023). The different forms of knowledge embodied by relevant and affected actors may rest on different epistemologies and may be founded on different interests, worldviews, and values. Exchanging, aligning, and harnessing different forms of knowledge in the pursuit of robust governance therefore requires the formation of arenas and interfaces whereby the actors can negotiate their varying types of knowledge to fill cognitive gaps, deal with cognitive uncertainty, promote joint learning, and, perhaps most importantly, manage ambiguities, inconsistencies, and conflicts. The cognitive negotiation of different forms of knowledge will often be complemented with a political alignment, as emerging problem definitions and solution strategies will acquire a particular legitimacy through the construction of provisional agreements between different actor groups. Negotiated knowledge exchange may spur contestation and conflict that may or may not stimulate mutual learning, but it may also promote joint sense-making vis-à-vis new disruptive events and observations (Maitlis and Sonenshein 2010; Weick 1988) and lead to the construction of a common ground that facilitates the co-creation of adaptive and innovative solutions (Pütz and Brassel 2021).

Based on these arguments, we define negotiated societal intelligence as the capacity to make governance decisions informed by different types of knowledge that are exchanged, aligned, and made actionable in and through negotiations with both cognitive and political aspects. Negotiated societal intelligence both deviates from the classical “linear model” of knowledge production, whereby scientists, separated from society, produce knowledge based on their own scientific paradigm, and the “relational model,” where scientists aim to incorporate experience and feedback from practitioners into their scientific knowledge on an ongoing basis. As such, it has more in common with the “emergent model” of knowledge production, where actionable knowledge emerges from somewhat chaotic and unscripted interactions in different arenas and interfaces in which facts and values are balanced with pragmatic concerns for solving pressing problems (see Gustafsson et al. 2017).

Turbulent emergency situations call for science to reduce uncertainty pertaining to the problems at hand and to provide evidence of the effectiveness of different context-dependent problem-solving strategies; however, the presence of unpredictable dynamics and crisis-induced time pressure work against “good science” capable of delivering valid and reliable answers (Van Dooren and Noordegraaf 2020). Moreover, the

knowledge asymmetries between relevant and affected actors are often huge, thus making it difficult to bring practical knowledge and political know-how to the fore (Philipps et al. 2023). It is therefore prudent to orchestrate knowledge exchange by bringing distributed actors together in arenas and interfaces that facilitate early warning, enable alignment of conflicting knowledge claims, bring forth new ideas that expand the toolbox, stimulate mutual learning and creative thinking, and harness their collective intelligence to design “adequate” solutions that can later be revised and adapted based on changing circumstances and new insights provided through feedback loops.

While citizen participation in science–policy interfaces (see Hove 2007) is important to ensure cognitive diversity and the contestation of elite knowledge, such participation cannot be taken for granted, since the exchange, alignment, and joint construction of knowledge take place at the intersection between science and political authority, which tends to exclude lay actors (Bäckstrand 2003). However, if the crisis-induced turbulence and/or government countermeasures have serious consequences for social and economic life, organizations representing different groups of citizens are likely to enter the debate, either by participating in an established interface, creating a new one, or making noise in the media (Mouter et al. 2021; Pearse 2020). If the latter is “loud” enough, it may secure organized groups of lay actors access to the science-policy interface, but there is always a risk that popular voices expressed via social media are excluded and become increasingly extremist, which undermines the legitimacy of public governance responses to turbulence.

The quality of the interaction between scientists, government officials, and lay actors in arenas facilitating negotiated societal intelligence may vary considerably (Putz and Brassel 2021). There will sometimes hardly be any negotiation of different knowledge claims, but merely some form of knowledge transfer between the involved actors. Knowledge transfer will sometimes be supplemented with the mutual contestation of knowledge claims that may lead to growing tensions or foster some degree of accommodation. When the interaction in knowledge interfaces is regular, dense, and involves a diversity of actors committed to joint problem-solving, it may even lead to the co-creation of adaptive and innovative governance solutions based on the negotiation of different forms of knowledge (see Dente et al. 2005); conceptualized here as *societal intelligence* (Kettle et al. 2014).

Drawing on these observations, we present four conjectures regarding the impact of negotiated societal intelligence on robust governance (see also Russo and van Dooren 2023):

1. Governance is more robust the more diverse the interfaces for negotiated societal intelligence are, the denser the interaction they spur, and the more they facilitate cognitive and political negotiation rather than mere knowledge transfer and mutual contestation.
2. Governance is more robust, the more that the interfaces of negotiated societal intelligence focus on early and nuanced detection of changes in problems and challenges.

3. Governance is more robust, the more that the interfaces of negotiated societal intelligence focus on expanding the solution space by bringing new feasible ideas and suggestions into play.
4. Governance is more robust, the more that the interfaces of negotiated societal intelligence focus on stimulating mutual learning and co-creating jointly supported solutions.

The four conjectures suggest that the quality and focus of negotiated societal intelligence taking place in institutionalized interfaces are key to enhancing robust governance.

3.4 | Exploring the Combined and Cumulative Impacts of the Three Governance Factors

The three governance factors can potentially relate to each other in multiple ways (see Ostrom 2007). One option would be that they do not affect each other. In this scenario, multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence would each have their separate and independent effect on robust governance. Although we cannot rule out this possibility, we do not think that the governance factors are completely isolated from each other, as networking is a common denominator.

A second possibility is that the presence of one factor may combine with one or two other factors to produce a positive joint impact that is greater than the sum of its parts. Two or three governance factors may strengthen each other and produce joint and cumulative impacts on robust governance. Hence, multi-level governance alone may enhance robust governance (Caponio et al. 2023; see also Carroll et al. 2023), but it may also expand the hybridity of public governance by providing the informal inspiration or formal recommendation of new tools and practices for application by local-level actors (Yasmin et al. 2022). Multi-level governance may also spur negotiated societal intelligence by stimulating interaction between relevant knowledge actors from multiple levels, for example, through the creation of a new multi-scalar knowledge interface (Homsy and Warner 2013). Likewise, governance hybridity aiming to combine different forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulation may support multi-level governance aimed at facilitating adaptation and innovation by going beyond hierarchical forms of regulation and governance based on substantive law produced by elected officials (Aliu et al. 2015). Governance hybridity that enhances the role of networks, deliberative democracy, and reflexive law may also support the formation or activation of knowledge interfaces that can construct negotiated societal intelligence that spurs robust governance in the face of multiscale challenges (Rathwell et al. 2015). Finally, negotiated societal intelligence may spur multi-level governance if local, regional, or national knowledge interfaces seek assistance from supranational or international expert agencies and invite them to join the conversation. Knowledge interfaces may also spur governance hybridity by facilitating mutual learning that expands the governance toolbox and suggests ways of mixing and matching different tools to adapt to innovate in the face of unpredictable dynamics. In sum, the three independent variables may have both individual and combined effects on robust governance.

A third option would be more of a configurational contingency approach (Lazzarini et al. 2020; Raab et al. 2015), where the presence (or absence) of one governance factor interacts with the presence (absence) of other governance factors to produce a particular set of conditions that enables robust governance to emerge. For example, poor multi-level governance may be compensated by very strong hybridity that allows local actors to be extremely creative when choosing governance tools, even if higher-level authorities do not support the transgression of the dominant governance paradigm and do not vouch for experimentation. Moreover, strong hybridity in the form of public governance may spur robust governance, even if there is poor hybridity in the forms of democracy, provided that negotiated societal intelligence is based on input from politicians, experts, and citizens. Since each of the three governance factors can be disaggregated into three or four key aspects that may be more or less absent, the number of possible combinations of different governance conditions is quite large.

We contend that, in practice, a mix of all three interaction modes will most likely occur. Each of the governance factors will have its own distinct impact on the prospects for robust governance, but they will also have joint effects and reinforce each other, and different mixes of present and absent governance conditions may achieve similar positive effects on robust governance. We therefore arrive at four propositions regarding the interaction between the three governance factors:

1. Each governance factor is likely to have some distinct positive impact on robust governance by itself.
2. The governance factors tend to interact to produce a joint impact, and the combination of governance factors will have a positive impact on robust governance that is greater than the sum of its parts due to their interaction (conjunctural causation).
3. Specific configurations of governance factors are likely to occur, with the presence of one specific governance factor (or aspects thereof) being tied to the absence of another specific factor (or aspects thereof), thereby providing a particular set of conditions for robust governance (asymmetry).
4. Different constellations of the governance conditions can produce similar degrees of robust governance (equifinality).

3.5 | The Contingent Conditions for Robust Governance

This study argues that the ability of social and political actors to govern robustly in turbulent times depends on three key governance factors: multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence. As seen above, extant theories support the idea that institutional forms of governance that enhance interaction between actors at multiple levels, the choice and combination of different forms and tools of governance, and the integration of different forms of knowledge into actionable insights will tend to be conducive to robust governance.

In reality, however, the highly contingent impact of the three governance factors complicates the provision of robust governance. First, different historical trajectories and political

cultures may explain the relative absence of one or more of the governance factors conducive to producing robust governance. Hence, some countries have unitary states that are only weakly integrated into supranational and global governance structures or have little devolution to local and regional levels of governance. Other countries may stubbornly stick to bureaucratic forms of governance, representative democracy, and formal law (and therefore score low on hybridity). The availability of knowledge interfaces supporting the construction of negotiated societal intelligence may also vary considerably between countries, depending on the presence of knowledge silos.

Second, robust governance may be hindered or mitigated by the presence of unmediated tensions between public and private actors from different levels; between different forms of governance, democracy, and legality; or between forms of knowledge based on contrasting epistemologies, which may hinder fruitful interaction and alignment. Robust governance hinges on productive vertical and horizontal interaction between relevant and affected actors and on their ability to combine different forms and tools of governance, but cross-boundary interaction may reactivate old grudges, trigger prejudice, and/or create conflicts, and the perceived incompatibility between different forms of governance, democracy, and legality may appear insurmountable.

Third, even when the three governance factors are present and may potentially combine to support robust governance, the responsible decisionmakers may not seize the moment because they are paralyzed by the heightened turbulence, or they may not have a clear sense of the need for flexible adaptation and proactive innovation, sticking instead to tried-and-true formats while accepting the failure to uphold public functions, purposes, and values. Moreover, public decisionmakers may not understand how multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence can be strengthened and harnessed to facilitate robust governance.

These observations allow us to modify our claim by willingly admitting that while different combinations of the three governance factors—multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence—may enable the robust governance of societal turbulence, there is no guarantee that the potentially positive impact of these governance factors will be realized in practice. Eschewing a systems-theoretical interpretation of how governance factors influence the politico-administrative system's response to heightened turbulence, we insist that robust governance is actor-driven. The three governance factors depicted at the bottom of Figure 1 condition (but do not determine) the real actors' pursuit of robust governance and their deployment of one or more robustness strategies. Moreover, the actors' ability to reflect critically on the conditions for robust governance and their strategic and transformative capacity determines whether they engage in proactive attempts at expanding the present and future scope for robust governance (Jessop 2002).

4 | Conclusion

This article asked how key governance factors, such as multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence, can contribute to the development of robust responses

to complex problems characterized by heightened turbulence. In answering this question, we first conceptualized societal turbulence and robust governance and showed how the latter can help to uphold key public functions, goals, and values in the face of the disruptions caused by heightened societal turbulence. We also presented a wide repertoire of robustness strategies upon which actors may draw in the pursuit of robust governance. We then surveyed relevant literatures to conceptualize multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence to show how these key governance factors, either alone or in different combinations, may enable social and political actors to enhance robust governance. The conceptual and theoretical analyses led to the formulation of a set of conjectures that focus on the impact of the three governance factors. The conclusion is that the presence of the three governance factors enables (without guaranteeing) the production of robust governance. While this was more or less what we expected from the outset, our analysis has produced a more fine-grained understanding of the impact of the three governance factors than we had imagined, since specific configurations of more or less present or absent aspects of one governance factor may ultimately combine with more or less present or absent aspects of the other governance factors, thereby providing a particular set of conditions conducive to robust governance. Different combinations may even have the same positive impact on the provision of robust governance.

At this early stage of new research on robust governance, this finding makes it difficult to provide precise recommendations to practitioners who are likely to face growing levels of turbulence in the future and will need to know how they should organize the public sector to support their pursuit of robust governance. We lack precise knowledge of the different configurations of present and absent aspects of the different governance factors that are likely to support robust governance. At this point, we can only recommend that practitioners broadly strengthen multi-level governance, hybrid governance, and negotiated societal intelligence so that these key governance factors can help bolster robust governance when the level of societal turbulence spikes. At a more concrete level, practitioners may proactively strengthen the governance role of public and private actors at multiple levels while establishing redundant vertical and horizontal connections that facilitate the adoption of whole-of-government and whole-of-society approaches to tackling crisis-induced turbulence based on adaptive and innovative responses. They may also officially embrace the coexistence of different institutional logics and policy tools while cultivating a mindset for pragmatically tailoring combinations of different forms of governance, democracy, and legal regulations to solve emerging problems. Finally, they may create knowledge interfaces in different policy fields and find ways of ensuring that lay actors can participate in meaningful ways and that different knowledge claims are negotiated in a constructive manner that helps to foster robust solutions.

It follows from the above that future research should conduct a configurational analysis of the impact of different aspects of the three governance factors on robust governance to determine more precisely the combinations of conditioning factors that may spur robust governance. Such an analysis will require access to large numbers of empirical cases, preferably drawn from

similar country types to keep contextual factors related to political regimes constant. It will also require careful operationalization and measurement. The analysis may be expanded by adding new governance variables and distinguishing between different types of turbulence that, for example, may be induced by different kinds of crises. Ultimately, the goal is to provide actionable knowledge about how different institutional forms of governance help to enhance robust governance in times of societal turbulence. The ultimate ambition is to identify different pathways to robust governance.

Ethics Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

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